

JOB BURNOUT IN HEALTHCARE: A CASE STUDY OF REGION II TRAUMA AND MEDICAL CENTER

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Job Burnout in Healthcare: A Case Study of Region II Trauma and Medical Center

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Abstract

This study investigated the job burnout prevalence at Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC) during the 2022-2023 academic year using descriptive- inferential research methods. Structured questionnaire was used to collect the data from R2TMC personnel, analyzed using statistical measures, including frequency counts, means, percentages, ranking, and Spearman's Correlation. Correlation analysis showed emotional exhaustion significantly correlated with salary grade, division, and nature of work. Depersonalization lacked significant correlations with examined variables. Personal accomplishment significantly correlated with salary grade, tenure, division, and staff classification. R2TMC personnel represent typical employees found in government-run medical hospitals, albeit with regional ethnic variations. They engage in diverse medical and administrative roles, often managing flexible schedules. High emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and low personal accomplishment contribute to job burnout severity. Nursing and medical staff experience higher emotional exhaustion, while those with higher salary grades or longer tenures display greater personal accomplishment and resilience. Recommendations include administrators investigating job burnout causes, examining work schedules, especially for nurses and midwives, developing strategies to reduce emotional exhaustion and depersonalization while enhancing personal accomplishment. Prioritizing emotional exhaustion among nursing and medical staff and bolstering personal accomplishment among all personnel are vital for resilience against job burnout. In summary, this study provides valuable insights into healthcare professionals' job burnout, laying a foundation for addressing and mitigating burnout challenges in the medical field.

Keywords: *emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, personal accomplishment, job burnout, human resource policy framework*

Introduction

Burnout is a phenomenon that has received considerable research attention in the past 50 years. As such, there is advanced knowledge of its prevalence, conceptualization, predictors, and outcomes. Although the literature has advanced research on burnout, this is still interesting to study. Burnout originated in the seventies but remains a contemporary problem because of persistent environmental stressors and challenges for employees and organizations as a whole. Although work is an important activity through which individuals may satisfy their basic psychological needs, the experience of work can sometimes become so overwhelming that it leads to job burnout – a combination of chronic exhaustion and a negative, cynical attitude towards work (Demerouti et al., 2021).

Job burnout is a perennial social problem that existed across countries for a long time (Schaufeli et al., 2009). It can be defined as a subliminal disorder brought by build-up stress from work and can carry various undesirable consequences for the workers and the organization. Studies have shown that burnout is associated with severe headaches, diabetes, cardiovascular problems, anxiety, depression, and insomnia (Lubbadeh, 2020). As such, job burnout could negatively impact the productivity of workers, their relationship with colleagues, their perception of their management, and even the quality of their lives. These could pose a tremendous challenge for administrators in managing their employees.

The Philippines as a developing tiger of Asia is not spared in the job-burnout experiences. Manila City has made it to the Top 10 cities in 53 countries with the highest risk of employees experiencing burnout. Even before the pandemic, studies on job burnout among healthcare facilities were also conducted (Gonzales, 2020). In the article, "Demographics and Personality Factors Associated with Burnout among Nurses in a Singapore Tertiary Hospital" Shin Yuh Ang (2016) stated that job rank has also been found to play a significant role in burnout, with literature suggesting that the higher an individual's rank is, the higher his scores on personal accomplishment. Age and experience have also been found to be significant and consistent factors. The older and more experienced an individual is, the higher his scores would be on personal accomplishment. Shift work, in particular night shifts, is purported to have a negative role in personal accomplishment. On the other hand, during the COVID-19 pandemic, healthcare workers experienced higher workloads, psychological suffering, social segregation, deficiency of incentives, absence of coordination, and proper management during their service among others. These healthcare professionals were confronted with difficulty in coping with these challenges due to situational and organizational factors. These workers were left with their faith in the Divine Mercy and mutual support to be the solutions to adapt to hardships. What is needed in this situation is adequate support addressing the problems faced by healthcare professionals. Therefore, determining the burnout level of healthcare professionals is deemed significant.

The predominant work-related stressor that occurs occasionally was workload while discrimination did not yield any response. The study of Dayrit & Jabonete (2018) yielded a moderate level of stress on the nine subscales while work-related stressors were significantly related to age, civil status, number of patients, and years in service. Nurses reported a moderate level of stress in all subscales of the modified, expanded nursing stress scale. They highly recommended effective coping mechanisms and stress

management programs and policies. It was also recommended to revisit the staffing and scheduling plan and provide enough personnel to cover the unit to address workload stressors.

Burnout is a syndrome conceptualized as resulting from chronic workplace stress that has not been successfully managed (WHO, 2019). It is characterized by three dimensions: feelings of energy depletion or exhaustion; increased mental distance from one's job, or feelings of negativism or cynicism related to one's job; and reduced professional efficacy. Burnout refers specifically to phenomena in the occupational context and should not be applied to describe experiences in other areas of life. The World Health Organization is about to embark on the development of evidence-based guidelines on mental well-being in the workplace.

Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC), being one of the end referral hospitals in Region II, has more than 1,000 permanent personnel and nearly 300 Contract of Service (COS) personnel. Though it offers also temporary appointments to Medical Doctors, some of them still resign from their positions. COS personnel, especially those in the Allied, Ancillary, and Nursing Divisions come and go. Some of them pursue overseas jobs, and some opted to transfer to other hospitals with no clear reasons.

Moreover, looking at the record on leave of absence of permanent personnel, a high number of processed leaves is noted. There are also employees who have incurred leave of absence without pay.

Looking at the grounds of job burnout, the study wanted to determine if there is job burnout among R2TMC personnel. These are the whys and wherefores upon which this study was grounded. The study explored the level of burnout among the personnel of R2TMC and related this to their sociodemographic profile and some identified work-related variables.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to find out the prevalence of burnout among R2TMC personnel. Hence, the following research questions were asked:

1. What is the sociodemographic profile of R2TMC personnel?
2. What is the work-related profile of Region II Trauma and Medical Center?
3. What is the burnout level of R2TMC employees?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the personnel's sociodemographic profiles and their burnout level?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the personnel's work-related variables and their burnout level?
6. What Human Resource Policy Framework could be recommended to mitigate job burnout among the R2TMC personnel?

Methodology

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational quantitative research design, as described by McBurney & White (2009). This approach aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of factors influencing job burnout among R2TMC employees while examining the relationships between burnout levels and sociodemographic and work-related variables. Descriptive analysis focused on profiling the respondents, while correlation analysis established significant relationships between the identified variables through hypothesis testing. Data were collected using a survey questionnaire.

The research was conducted at Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC), formerly Veterans Regional Hospital, located in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. R2TMC, a 500-bed capacity hospital, serves Nueva Vizcaya and neighboring provinces, providing equitable and quality healthcare for over a century. The facility includes multiple major and secondary buildings that house various medical and administrative units.

The study population consisted of 1,447 R2TMC employees, including regular and contract personnel. A sample size of 313 respondents was determined using Slovin's formula, ensuring proportional representation across divisions. Respondents were selected randomly, with distribution based on Human Resource Management Office data.

The Maslach Burnout Inventory Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS) for Health Personnel was used to assess burnout. The tool measures three dimensions—Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Personal Accomplishment—using a 7-point Likert scale. The scoring matrix was based on a prior study by Estabillo (2020), classifying burnout levels as low, moderate, or high.

Permission and ethical clearance were obtained before conducting the study. Respondents were informed of the study's purpose, and their consent was secured. Surveys were administered both online and offline, with a validated Tagalog version available. Data collection took place over one month, and completed questionnaires were securely stored and later discarded following data extraction.

The study employed percentage and frequency to analyze demographic data, mean and standard deviation to measure burnout levels, and correlation procedures to examine relationships between variables.

The study maintained respondent confidentiality and anonymity through coded data and secure storage methods. Participation was voluntary, with no direct benefits or risks to respondents. Ethical clearance was granted by the R2TMC Institutional Review Board. The study, funded by the researcher, aims to inform HR strategies to address burnout among R2TMC personnel and contributes to the development of workplace well-being policies.

Results and Discussion

This section contains the presentation analysis and interpretation of data. These include brief discussions on the sociodemographic profile of the respondents and work-related variables, their level of burnout, and the relationships between the variables. The arrangement of the presentation and discussion of the results are based on the objectives of the study.

Sociodemographic Profile

The sociodemographic profile of the respondents is described in the study as to their age, gender, civil status, intercultural community or ethnicity, position, salary grade, years in the organization, division (medical/non-medical), area of assignment, and status of appointment. These were presented in distinct tables and described separately.

Age. Table 1 shows the frequency and percent distribution of the respondents according to their age.

Table 1. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
21-29	98	31.2
30-39	157	50.3
40-49	38	12.2
50-59	17	5.2
60-above	3	0.9
Total	313	100.0

Mean = 33.95 SD = 7.88 Minimum = 22 Maximum = 61

The above table indicates that half of the number of respondents belong to the 30 – 39 age bracket (50.3%), followed by those in the 21-29 years of age, 40-49 years old (12.2%), and 50-59 age brackets. Only few were in the 60 and above category. The average age of the respondents is almost 34 years, where the youngest is 22 and the oldest is 61 years of age. The result of the study indicated that most of the respondents were 21-39 years old. This reflects the massive hiring of the hospital due to the expansion of its services and infusion of younger personnel into the workforce.

Gender. Table 2 presents the frequency and percent distribution of the respondents according to gender.

The table denotes that majority of the respondents are females (62.6%) followed by males (33.9%); however, some of the respondents claimed to belong to the LGBTQ++ community (3.5%). The result of the study confirms the observation made by the Human Resources Management Office of the R2TMC that there are more female employees than their male counterpart. The result further established the gender groupings that members of the LGBTQ++ community can also be found and accepted in medical institutions, as in other agencies and institutions in the country.

Table 2. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Female	196	62.6
Male	106	33.
LBTQ++	11	3.5
Total	313	100.0

Civil Status. The frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to civil status are depicted in Table 3.

As reflected in the table, the majority of the R2TMC personnel who served as respondents are married (52.7%), followed by those who are single (42.8%). Only some of them were into common law marriage (2.6%), widowed (1.3%), or separated (0.6%). The average age of the respondents may probably be related to the civil status of the respondents. Since most of the respondents are 21-39 years old, the older ones were believed to be married while the younger ones were still single, especially those aged 20- 29 years old. On the other hand, the older respondents were believed to be those who are widowed.

Table 3. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to civil status*

<i>Civil Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Married	165	52.7
Single	134	42.8
Common Law/Live-in	8	2.6
Widowed	4	1.3
Separated	2	0.6
Total	313	100.0

Ethnicity. In this study, ethnicity is also termed as an intercultural community. The frequency and percent distribution of respondents

according to ethnicity are depicted in Table 4.

The table below indicated that the personnel of the R2TMC are a conglomeration of various ethnic groups. However, the majority of them are Ilocano (55.6%) and Ilocanos with mixed ethnicity (8.0%) also constituted a considerable portion of the number of respondents; followed by the Ifugao/Igorot/Isinai group (9.6%), Gaddang (16%), and Tagalog (4.2%). Other intercultural communities, aside from those stipulated above, constitute 17.6% of the total respondents. It is not surprising that the respondents of the study are of diverse ethnicities because they represent the observed multi-ethnic characteristic of the Province of Nueva Vizcaya and its adjacent provinces where the R2TMC emanated.

Table 4. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to ethnicity*

<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Ilocano	174	55.6
Ifugao/Igorot/Isinai	30	9.6
Ilocano with mixed ethnicity	25	8.0
Gaddang	16	5.1
Tagalog	13	4.2
Others	55	17.6
Total	313	100.0

Position. Table 5 portrays the frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to position.

In this study, position pertains to the classification of the plantilla position of the respondents and where they are actually working. The table shows that the biggest group of the respondents are in nursing (43.1%), followed by administrative (24.6%), allied and ancillary (16.9%), clinical (11.8%), and other positions (3.5%), respectively. Since medical institutions like the R2TMC host various medical and other related services, the multifarious role of nurses is needed in almost all of the major services offered by it. Hence, the largest group in medical institutions is usually in nursing.

Table 5. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to position*

<i>Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Nursing	135	43.1
Administrative	77	24.6
Allied and ancillary	53	16.9
Clinical	37	11.8
other position	11	3.5
Total	313	100.0

Salary grade. The frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to Salary Grade are shown in Table 6.

The table below shows that the salary grades of the respondents of the study are fully distributed in various salary grade brackets identified in the study. The lowest salary grade is SG 2, while the highest is SG 25, usually for doctors/physicians or medical specialists. Salary grades correspond to remuneration received by personnel in government institutions. Hence, the variety of salary grades indicate that the study spanned various respondents with divergent compensations indicating that the study has extensive coverage among R2TMC personnel.

Table 6. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to salary grade*

<i>Salary Grade</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
1-5	44	14.1
6-10	74	23.7
11-15	98	31.4
16-20	58	18.6
21-25	39	12.4
Total	313	100.0

Mean = 12 SD = 6 Minimum = 2 Maximum = 25

Years employed in the R2TMC. As reflected in Table 7, the frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to the number of years employed in R2TMC are described herein.

The table denotes that the majority of the R2TMC personnel who served as respondents have been employed for five (5) years and below (63.5%), followed by those who have been in the medical institution for 6-10 years (26.9%). A smaller number of respondents has been connected with the medical institution for more than 10 years. The minimum length of service of the respondents is one (1) year and the maximum is 34 years or with the average number of years the respondents are employed in R2TMC is five (5) years. The result indicates that the rapid development and expansion of services offered by the R2TMC necessitates the hiring of new personnel, and most of the employees have been employed within 10 years.

Table 7. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to number of years employed in R2TMC*

<i>Number of Years in R2TMC</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
1-5	199	63.5
6-10	84	26.9
11-15	11	3.6
16-20	12	3.9
21-25	4	1.2
36-above	3	0.90
Total	313	100.0

Mean = 5.10 SD = 5.36 Minimum = 1 Maximum = 34

Division. Table 8 presents the frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to the division where they are located within R2TMC.

The table indicates that the biggest group of respondents came from the nursing division (40.3%), followed by the medical (36.7%), OMCC (8.6%), HOPS (8.6%), and finance (5.8%) divisions, respectively. Again, the result reflects that since R2TMC is a medical center, most of the personnel would also be classified under the nursing and medical divisions.

Table 8. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to division*

<i>Division</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Nursing	126	40.3
Medical	115	36.7
OMCC	27	8.6
HOPS	27	8.6
Finance	18	5.8
Total	313	100.0

Assignment. The frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to the assignment are shown in Table 9.

Again, the table below denotes that in terms of assignment, the biggest group of respondents are assigned to the nursing (41.9%) and medical (35.8%) divisions, followed by those in the OMCC (8.6%), administrative (8.0%), and finance (5.8%), respectively. Since most of the services offered by the medical center are medical services, it also follows that most of the personnel are being assigned to the nursing and medical divisions.

Table 9. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to assignment*

<i>Assignment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Nursing	131	41.9
Medical	112	35.8
OMCC	27	8.6
Administrative	25	8.0
Finance Section	18	5.8
Total	313	100.0

Status of appointment. Table 10 presents the frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to the status of the appointment.

Based on the table below, the majority of the respondents are holding permanent positions (66.1%), followed by those with contract of service (25.6%), and temporary (8.3%) statuses, respectively. The data indicated that the biggest number of the personnel in R2TMC is holding plantilla positions in permanent or regular status during the time the study was conducted. However, a considerable number are still classified as COS and some temporary appointments. This trend is also prevalent in various government offices where the need for personnel is urgent but the plantilla positions to hire them are not yet present; hence, the government agencies resorted to hiring contract of service personnel.

Table 10. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to the status of appointment*

<i>Status of Appointment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Permanent	207	66.1
Contract of Service	80	25.6
Temporary	26	8.3
Total	313	100.0

Work-related Variables

The work-related variables include the variables that are actually involved in the professional careers or work within R2TMC. These

include staff or personnel classification, their nature of work, and work schedule. These were presented and discussed separately in the study.

Staff classification. The frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to staff classification are reflected in Table 11.

Table 11. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to staff classification*

<i>Staff Classification</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Medical	198	63.3
Non-Medical	115	36.7
Total	313	100.0

The table denotes that of the two staff classifications identified in the study, the majority is categorized under the medical staff (63.3%), followed by those of the non- medical staff (36.7%). As emphasized in previous discussions, since the R2TMC is a medical center, the majority of the personnel is classified under the medical staff, and proportionate to this, more respondents were from such a staff category.

Nature of work. The frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to the nature of work are reflected in Table 12.

As shown in the table, the largest group of respondents based on the nature of work is nursing (37.4%) composed of nurses and midwives, followed by those categorized under the administrative staff (22%), comprised of HOPS and finance group; clinical (11.8%), classified as doctors or physicians; support staff (11.2%), composed of nursing attendants and administrative aides; ancillary (8.9%), comprised of DMD, MD, RMT, and RRT; allied (7.7%) composed of the RT, PT, PPh, ND, Psy, HP, and SWO; and the janitorial services (1%), respectively.

The result denotes a wide variety of work the respondents were involved in. This is preferable because the data were not only limited to some persons with specialized works; instead, the scope of work gives more extensive data coverage and their reactions to levels of job burnout might vary.

Table 12. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to nature of work*

<i>Nature of Work</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Nursing (Nurse, Midwife)	117	37.4
Administrative Staff (HOPS/Finance)	69	22.0
Clinical (Physicians)	37	11.8
Support Staff (Nursing Attendant, Administrative Aide)	35	11.2
Ancillary (DMD, MD, RMT, RRT)	28	8.9
Allied (RT, PT, PPh, ND, Psy, HP, SWO)	24	7.7
Janitorial	3	1.0
Total	313	100.0

Work schedule. The variable work schedules of the respondents are reflected in Table 13.

The table indicates that half of the total number of respondents perform regular eight (8) hours of duty and physical reporting during the prescribed regular day of the week and time (50.8%), followed by those having 12 hours of duty rotation (38%), 24 hours duty (6.1%), 32 hours duty (4.2%), and teleconsult duty (1%). Those with regular duty are the administrative and finance group; while those with varied schedules have been performing technical functions needed at all times, especially during emergencies.

Table 13. *Frequency and percent distribution of respondents according to work schedule*

<i>Work Schedule</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
8 hours duty (Physical Reporting - daily)	159	50.8
12 hours duty rotation (AM/PM)	119	38.0
24 hours duty	19	6.1
32 hours duty	13	4.2
Teleconsult Duty	3	1.0
Total	313	100.0

Levels of Burnout

The level of job burnout of R2TMC personnel was measured in terms of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. These were presented distinctly and discussed in detail. The job burnout variables are presented using different criteria and scales to measure their level.

Emotional Exhaustion. The first variable in measuring the job burnout level of the R2TMC personnel was emotional exhaustion. Table 14 shows the frequency and percent distribution of R2TMC personnel on the level of job burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion.

Table 14. Frequency and percent distribution of R2TMC personnel on the level of job burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion

Emotional Exhaustion			
Level of Burnout	Scale	Frequency	Percent
Low	0-18	92	29.4
Moderate	19-26	87	27.8
High	27-above	134	42.6
Total		313	100

The table indicates that of the 313 respondents of the study, 134 (42.6%) are suffering from high job burnout levels in terms of emotional exhaustion, followed by those suffering from low (92 or 29.4%), and moderate (87 or 27.8%) levels, respectively. This is a cause of concern because a large majority of the R2TMC personnel have been either suffering from moderate to high levels of job burnout on emotional exhaustion. The biggest group of personnel are suffering from high levels of emotional exhaustion. This means that they are in a condition of feeling emotionally drained and worn out as a result of accumulated stress from personal or work life. The moderate and high burnout level of emotional exhaustion can cause undesirable consequences for the workers and the organization. Building upon the research carried out by Wullur & Werang (2020), their study also sheds light on the prevalence of emotional burnout among teachers in Merauke, Indonesia. Their findings underscored the increasing challenges associated with the teaching profession, which has become notably demanding and emotionally taxing, particularly in the context of the ongoing pandemic.

Table 15 further identifies which areas of concern contributed to the job burnout levels currently being experienced by the R2TMC personnel.

The table generally classifies that the level of job burnout of the respondents in terms of emotional exhaustion is high (mean = 27.04), which is really alarming. In order to identify which contributed more to the job burnout level of the respondents in terms of emotional exhaustion, the mean of the indicators was determined and ranked. The result denoted that those contributed more to the level of job burnout on emotional exhaustion include the personnel’s feeling of being used up at the end of a work day, with the impression that they were at the end of their rope of endurance. This might probably be due to their observation that they were working too hard on their job which induced the impression of being burned out from their work. Because of this, they feel emotionally drained and still feel tired when they get up in the morning and have to face another day on their job.

The consequences of stipulated conditions can have serious consequences for the organization or agency. Emotionally burned-up workers are so depressed and unmotivated with their jobs that it may be difficult for them or impossible to improve motivation and performance. Workers who are burned out should be provided with renewing experiences through team building and time-outs from their work to bring back their motivation to work satisfactorily on their jobs.

Table 15. A detailed presentation on the level of job burnout of R2TMC personnel in terms of emotional exhaustion

Emotional Exhaustion	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank and Qualitative Description
1. I feel used up at the end of a work day.	4.53	1.95	1
2. I feel that I am at the end of my rope.	3.33	2.05	2
3. I feel I am working too hard on my job.	2.85	1.93	3
4. I feel burned out from my work.	2.82	1.93	4
5. I feel emotionally drained from my work.	2.82	1.89	5
6. I feel tired when I get up in the morning and have to face another day on the job.	2.79	1.88	6
7. Working with people directly puts too much stress on me.	2.70	1.82	7
8. I feel frustrated by my job.	2.65	1.81	8
9. Working with people all day is really a strain for me.	2.55	1.75	9
Level of Burnout	27.04	17.01	High

Note: 0-16=Low; 17-26=Moderate; Above 27=High

Depersonalization. The results of the assessment of the level of job burnout in terms of depersonalization were presented in Table 16 and Table 17.

The table shows that 128 (42.6%) of the 313 respondents are suffering from low job burnout levels in terms of depersonalization, followed by those suffering from high (118 or 37.7%), and moderate (99 or 31.7%) job burnout levels, respectively. The result indicates that still, the majority of the respondents have been either suffering from high to moderate levels of job burnout in terms of depersonalization.

Table 16. Frequency and percent distribution of R2TMC personnel on the level of job burnout in terms of depersonalization

Level of Burnout	Scale	Frequency	Percent
Low	0 – 5	128	40.9
Moderate	6 – 11	99	31.7
High	12 - above	118	37.7
Total		313	100.0

Contrary to the moderate level of burnout observed among the respondents, the study conducted by Bosnia & Herzegovina (2014) revealed that 15% of the medical doctors who participated in their research exhibited a high level of depersonalization. Mean while, a moderate level of depersonalization was evident in about half of the respondents. This study underscores that depersonalization has been a significant issue among medical doctors and represents an important factor in regulating workplace stress. Furthermore, cynicism is a notable factor that has been shown to reduce empathy in patients' interactions with healthcare workers (Pranjic & Bilic, 2014).

Depersonalization is also called cynicism or pessimism in other research. This is defined in the study as a doubtful and cold attitude towards customers and the forfeiture of the personal component in dealing with individuals. Since R2TMC is a service-oriented government agency, cynicism, pessimism or sarcasm as a by-product of depersonalization will stain the reputation of the institution as well as the job satisfaction of the employees.

To identify which areas of concern contributed to the job burnout levels currently being experienced by the R2TMC personnel in terms of depersonalization, the indicators used in the study were ranked, and the overall mean was qualitatively measured. The result of the detailed assessment is revealed in Table 17.

As reflected in the Table 17, the level of job burnout of the respondents in terms of depersonalization is indicated by the mean value of 10.72, which is qualitatively described as moderate. The result indicates that, usually, the personnel of the R2TMC who served as respondents of the study may sometimes display a cold attitude towards their clients. This may be caused by too much stress from dealing with the unruly behaviors of patients and their watchers.

Based on the result of the study, this attitude of the respondents is being brought about by burnout. This resulted in cynicism wherein these personnel will sometimes no longer care what may happen to some patients or clients treating them as if they were impersonal objects and not people. Too much stress from dealing with their unruly clients will make them more callous toward people which may result in hardening their emotions and becoming less caring to the patients they promise to serve wholeheartedly.

Table 17. A detailed presentation on the level of job burnout of R2TMC personnel in terms of depersonalization

<i>Depersonalization</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Rank and Qualitative Description</i>
1. I don't really care what happens to some patients/clients.	2.36	1.65	1
2. I feel I treat some patients/clients as if they were impersonal objects	2.23	1.54	2
3. I worry that this job is hardening me emotionally.	2.10	1.51	3
4. I've become more callous toward people since I took this job.	2.05	1.53	4
5. I feel patients/clients blame me for some of their problems.	1.98	1.50	5
Level of Burnout	10.72	7.73	Moderate

Note: 0-6=Low; 7-12=Moderate; Above 13=High

Often depersonalization follows from emotional exhaustion. When a person no longer has the energy to deal with people, he naturally starts to withdraw from them and treats them as objects. Such may result in inharmonious dealing with people or clients, especially medical patients. This often has grim consequences on the reputation of the institution. Hence, administrators and HR should look into the case, and job burnout on depersonalization should be addressed.

Personal Accomplishment. Table 18 displays the result of the assessment on the level of job burnout in terms of reduced accomplishment.

The table below shows that of the 313 respondents, 159 (50.86%) are suffering from low job burnout level in terms of reduced personal accomplishment, followed by those suffering from high (129 or 41.2%) and moderate (25 or 7.9%) job burnout levels, respectively. The result indicates that a little less than half of the respondents are either suffering from high or moderate levels of job burnout in terms of reduced personal accomplishments while the rest claimed to have low levels of burnout.

Table 18. Frequency and percent distribution of R2TMC personnel on the level of job burnout in terms of reduced personal accomplishment

<i>Level of Burnout</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Low	40-above	159	50.8
Moderate	34-39	25	7.9
High	0-33	129	41.2
Total		313	100.0

Reduced personal accomplishment is defined in the study as professional inefficacy and it refers to the employee's propensity to negatively assess themselves and a deep sense of ineffectiveness in work and interaction with others. This can be caused by many factors related to their jobs.

To determine areas of concern that contributed to the job burnout levels currently being experienced by the R2TMC personnel in terms of reduced personal accomplishment, indicators used in the study were ranked and the overall mean was qualitatively measured. The result of the detailed assessment is revealed in Table 19.

As reflected in the table, the level of job burnout of the respondents in terms of personal accomplishment is indicated by the mean value of 29.91, which is qualitatively described as low. The result indicates that, usually, the personnel of the R2TMC who served as respondents of the study consider themselves to have a low level of personal accomplishments.

The questionnaire asked the respondents if they can comprehend the feelings of the client, if the member can deal effectively with the client’s glitches, if the participant can create a relaxed atmosphere for the client, if the participant feels exhilarated working closely with recipients, if they feel like they accomplished many worthwhile things on the job, and if the participant can deal calmly with the emotional problems of the client. Since the result indicated that the personal accomplishments of the respondents are low, the level of reduced personal accomplishment is high.

Relatively, Maslach et al. (1996) stated the following: “In contrast to the subscales of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, where the severity increases as the scores increase, the severity of the lack of a sense of personal accomplishment decreases as the score increases.”

Additionally, a study titled "The Association Between Self-Efficacy and Feelings of Reduced Personal Accomplishment among Female Teachers in South-Eastern Nigeria" uncovered a finding that aligns with the results of the present study. This research revealed a positive relationship between self-efficacy and the experience of reduced personal accomplishment, mirroring the outcomes observed here. The study participants were selected through random sampling, comprising 25 young and 25 adult teachers, all falling within the age range of 25-35 years and above, with a mean age of 18.8 years (Nwankwo, Obi, & Aboh, 2013).

Table 19. A detailed presentation on the level of job burnout of R2TMC personnel in terms of personal accomplishment

Personal Accomplishment	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank and Qualitative
			Description
1. I have accomplished many worthwhile things in this job.	3.82	2.37	1
2. I can easily create a relaxed atmosphere with my patients/clients.	3.79	2.35	2
3. In my work, I deal with emotional problems very calmly.	3.74	2.37	3
4. I can easily understand how patients feel about things.	3.74	2.33	4
5. I feel exhilarated after working closely with my patients.	3.74	2.31	5
6. I feel I’m positively influencing other people’s lives through my work.	3.71	2.29	6
7. I deal very effectively with the problems of my patients/clients.	3.68	2.26	7
8. I feel very energetic.	3.68	2.30	8
Level of Burnout	29.91	24.0	Low

Note: 0-31=Low; 32-38=Moderate; Above 39=High

Relationship between the R2TMC personnel’s sociodemographic profiles, work- related variables and their burnout level

To determine if there is a significant relationship between the R2TMC personnel’s sociodemographic profiles, work-related variables, and their job burnout level, the correlation procedure, specifically Spearman rho, was used. The result of the statistical analysis is shown in Table 20.

The relationships between the dependent and independent variables are discussed as presented in the Table 20. The R2TMC personnel’s sociodemographic profiles, work-related variables, and job burnout level is presented and discussed per category.

Table 20. Relationship between the sociodemographic profiles, work-related variables, and job burnout level of R2TMC personnel (n = 313)

Sociodemographic & Work-related variables		Job Burnout Level			
		Emotional Exhaustion	Depersonalization	Personal Accomplishment	
Sociodemographic	Age	r	-0.014	0.029	0.084
		p	0.804	0.607	0.137
Gender		r	0.058	0.032	0.001
		p	0.307	0.567	0.980
Civil status		r	-0.065	0.016	-0.053
		p	0.252	0.775	0.348
Ethnicity		r	-0.089	-0.017	-0.024
		p	0.115	0.769	0.678
Position		r	0.009	0.016	-0.091
		p	0.880	0.776	0.109
Salary Grade		r	.209**	0.035	.309**
		p	0.000	0.537	0.000
No. Years in R2TMC		r	0.050	0.049	.165**
		p	0.382	0.390	0.003
Division		r	.167**	0.014	.196**
		p	0.003	0.799	0.000
Assignment		r	0.102	-0.013	0.106

	p	0.070	0.825	0.060
Appointment	r	-0.085	-0.045	0.056
	p	0.135	0.432	0.321
Work-related Variables				
Staff Classification	r	-0.016	0.034	-.181**
	p	0.776	0.543	0.001
Nature of Work	r	.141*	0.086	-0.018
	p	0.012	0.130	0.748
Schedule	r	-0.011	0.043	0.037
	p	0.847	0.447	0.510

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Emotional exhaustion. The level of job burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion significantly correlated only with the profile variables salary grade ($r = 0.209$, $p = <0.001$), and division ($r = 0.167$, $p = 0.003$); and for the work-related variables, only the nature of work ($r = 0.141$, $p = 0.012$) significantly correlated with the dependent variable. The positive correlation coefficient (r) between the variables implies direct relationships. Hence, it can be inferred from the result that the personnel of the R2TMC who have higher salary grades, or the personnel in the nursing and medical group have higher levels of job burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion. Likewise, for work-related variables, the result implies that those who work in the nursing division such as nurses and midwives, and those in the administrative staff such as those in the HOPS and finance also have higher levels of job burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion.

Relatively, emotional exhaustion is known in the medical field as the state of feeling exhausted, unfulfilled, and worn out because of the continued depletion of emotive resources from overstretched work (Nie, Du, Liu, Yuan, & Ma, 2020) due to challenging work schedules. This can also be due to inadequate competency to meet the demands of the work (Tourigny, Baba, Han, & Wang, 2012). Aside from medical fields, emotional exhaustion is also prevalent in the hospitality and service industry, particularly in the call center industry (Puyod & Charoensukmongkol, 2019). Similarly, Cafasso (2021) stated that clinical studies show that emotional exhaustion is a feeling of emotionally drained and worn-out as a result of accrued stress from personal lives or work-related stuff, or a combination of both. Emotional exhaustion is an indicator of burnout. People who experience emotional exhaustion frequently feel like they have no control or power over what is happening in life. This may be due to a deficiency of energy, decreased motivation, and poor sleep. This chronic, stressed-out state can be source of permanent impairment to health; and long-term anxiety causes emotional exhaustion. People who experience emotional exhaustion may feel lack of motivation, irritability, feelings of hopelessness, apathy, headaches, nervousness, irrational anger, sense of dread, trouble sleeping, physical fatigue, absentmindedness, change in appetite, and difficulty concentrating, increased cynicism, or pessimism, and depression.

Depersonalization. The result of the statistical analysis indicates that neither the profile nor work-related variables used in the study significantly correlated with the level of job burnout in terms of depersonalization. Hence, depersonalization did not significantly correlate with any of the profile and work-related variables.

To this, Pranjic & Bilic (2014) stated that the perception of depersonalization predicted the following stressors: the need to use knowledge and skills during working tasks; work has phases that are too difficult; and job dissatisfaction was linked with awareness of depersonalization. In conclusion, the study underlines that depersonalization is an important factor in the way to regulate stress in the workplace. Cynicism is a significant factor that reduced empathy in patients' approaches to healthcare workers. It seemed that missing continued education in hospitals, too.

Personal accomplishment. The level of personal accomplishment significantly correlated with the profile variables salary grade ($r = 0.309$, $p = <0.001$), number of years employed in R2TMC ($r = 0.165$, $p = 0.003$), and division ($r = 0.196$, $p = <0.001$); and work-related variable staff classification ($r = -0.181$, $p = 0.001$). The positive correlation coefficients between salary grade and number of years employed in R2TMC denotes those personnel with higher salary grades, or those who have been employed in the R2TMC for longer periods, as well as those in the nursing division have higher levels of personal accomplishments. However, the negative correlation coefficient between staff classification and the dependent variable implies that non-medical staffs appear to have higher levels of personal accomplishments than those categorized under the medical staff.

Maslach et al. (1996) emphasized that personal accomplishment or self-efficacy is the belief in one's capabilities to establish and perform the courses of action needed to achieve prospective circumstances. In a nutshell, self-efficacy is an individual's belief in his or her ability to prosper in a particular circumstance. Bandura (1992) stated that one of the foundations of self-efficacy is mastery of experiences which is the most operative way of developing a durable sense of efficacy. Executing a task positively strengthens individual's sense of self-efficacy, while failing to deal with a task can weaken self-efficacy. Similarly, in a personal blog of Rozin (2020), she identifies common causes of inefficiency at the workplace: poor fit between the person in the position and the organization; a disconnect between cause and effect, work, and outcome; lack of clarity regarding how responsibility is assigned; nepotism; absence of feedback; deficiency in communication; time management; and wasteful processes. The study of Bakker et al. (2005) revealed that burnout dimensions such as: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment has a contagion effect. Older age workers get worse self-rated health, and age shows an inverse relation to psychological health. Hsu (2018) recommended interventions to support older employees.

Conclusions

Based on the salient findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The respondents are typical employees who can be found in any government-run medical hospitals throughout the country with regional peculiarities in terms of ethnicity.

The respondents of the study were typical medical personnel performing diversified medical-related and administrative work either with regular or flexible work schedules.

The levels of job burnout of the employees on emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, coupled with their low personal accomplishment increased the severity of burnout experienced.

R2TMC personnel in the nursing and medical group have higher levels of job burnout in terms of emotional exhaustion. However, personnel with higher salary grades, or those who have been employed in the R2TMC for longer periods have higher levels of personal accomplishments and are more resilient to burnout.

Based on the salient findings of the study and the above conclusions, the following are recommended:

Employees in government-run medical hospitals throughout the country are prone to job burnout; hence, the administrators through the HRM Office should study the causes and alleviate such job burnout for the health and productivity of their personnel.

The work schedules of nurses and midwives, and other medical personnel, should be studied to lessen the continuous work hours they dispense per day in order to lessen the burnout they experienced in their job.

Effective strategies should be found by the hospital administrators and the HRMO to lessen the levels of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization and to increase the personal accomplishment of the R2TMC personnel to alleviate the burnout they experience in their job.

To mitigate job burnout among R2TMC personnel, alleviating the emotional exhaustion experienced by the nursing and medical should be prioritized. Personal accomplishments of all R2TMC personnel should also be enhanced for them to be more resilient to job burnout.

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